

Analysing Student Projects in Mobile Cartography: Trends, User Expectations and Educational Insights

Eva Hauthal, Jakob Listabarth, Dirk Burghardt

TUD Dresden University of Technology, Institute of Cartography, Germany
eva.hauthal@tu-dresden.de, jakob.listabarth@tu-dresden.de,
dirk.burghardt@tu-dresden.de

Abstract. This work in progress explores student projects that have been submitted since 2012 as part of a university course called ‘Mobile Cartography’ offered as an elective module for master's programmes. These projects are native mobile map applications on a self-selected, space-related topic. Systematically analysing these projects in terms of their design, content, map implementation and geographic reference promises to provide insights into the habits and expectations of young people with regard to mobile map applications if they themselves have the opportunity to create such an app and thus fill a gap. The analysis also reflects general developments in design patterns, app functionalities and possible areas of application. These findings can be useful both for academic teaching and for app development in practice.

Keywords. mobile cartography, mobile maps, students projects

1. Introduction

The rise of smartphones and their continuous technical advancements have profoundly impacted how people communicate, capture memories, access information and navigate in their surroundings. Mobile map applications simplify tasks such as traveling, finding spatial data and orienting oneself. Given this, integrating the supply of spatial information on mobile devices in the curriculum of geoinformatics or cartography-oriented study programmes is both relevant and modern.

Since 2012, the one-semester course ‘Mobile Cartography’ at TUD Dresden University of Technology in Dresden (Germany) has focused on approaches,

Published in “Proceedings of the 19th International Conference on Location Based Services (LBS 2025)”, edited by Juha Oksanen, Henrikki Tenkanen, Pyry Kettunen and Ville Mäkinen, LBS 2025 7-9 May 2025 Otaniemi, Espoo, Finland.

This contribution underwent double-blind peer review based on the paper.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15351267>
© Authors 2025. CC BY 4.0 License.

methods and applications for information delivery and cartographic presentation on mobile devices. The theory is taught in weekly lectures, while practical skills are imparted in weekly exercises, which focus on programming mobile map applications for the Android operating system. The gained programming skills in particular, but also the theoretical knowledge, will be synthesised in a final project to be completed and submitted by up to four students. This project is a mobile Android map application on a freely chosen spatial topic. The course is part of the in-house Geoinformation Technologies master's program and the international cooperation master's program Cartography, with 70% of attending students coming from the latter. Since 2012, 344 students from 64 countries have submitted 134 apps.

Figure 1. Percentages of app categories in student map apps (2012 - 2024), downloads of mobile apps worldwide (2019 - 2024) (Statistica 2023) and available apps in Google Play Store (2nd quarter 2024) (Statistica 2024).

An analysis of all these apps is currently a work in progress. The following will provide first insights into the thematic categories, the user interface (UI) design, the map implementation and the geographic reference. This allows to conclude which design and usage preferences students reveal when developing mobile map applications and how these trends are reflected in mobile cartography in general.

2. Mobile App Analysis

2.1. App Categories

The categorisation of the student projects is based on thematic content and the task of the map. To define the thematic categories, scientific literature (Huang & Benyoucef 2023; Huseynov 2020; Xu et al. 2016), statistical data and categories from major app stores were used, resulting in 22 distinct categories as shown in Figure 1. The top six categories in student apps are travel (18%), tools or utilities (15%), education (11%), food & drink (10%), games (8%) and health & fitness (11%). Figure 1 also shows statistics on global mobile app download numbers (Statistica 2023) representing usage, i.e. demand, and on available apps in Google Play Store (Statistica 2024) representing supply. In some categories, there are strong deviations between the shares of student apps and the two presented statistics, likely because student projects are required to include a map, making certain categories more suitable than others.

Since 2019, the global proportions of thematic categories per year have remained stable (Statistica 2023), while the student app categories show great yearly fluctuations (Figure 2), which is certainly also due to the lower number compared to the aforementioned statistics, which range in the millions. Despite this, travel apps have remained a dominant category, though they have declined over time, as have tools or utilities, education and health & fitness. Conversely, food & drink and games have shown an upward trend.

Categorising according to map tasks (collection, exploration, location finding and navigation (Gaigg 2023)) shows that collection apps became prominent from 2017 onward (Figure 3). Collection apps are mainly found in the lifestyle or productivity categories in the form of various types of diaries.

Figure 2. Temporal development of the top six thematic app categories of all student mobile map applications.

2.2. User Interface Design Patterns

An investigation of the implemented mobile UI design patterns (Perea & Giner 2017) reflects when students became familiar with newly introduced design patterns and therefore incorporated them into their apps themselves. For example, the Floating Action Button, introduced in 2014, has been used in student apps since 2015. The hamburger menu, available since 2011, appeared in student projects starting in 2014. However, dialogues, present since the first Android version in 2008, have been part of student apps since the course ‘Mobile Cartography’ began in 2012.

2.3. Map Implementation

98% of student apps use point data, only 17% use line data and 12% area data. Therefore, markers are the most common visualisation method, often with info pop-ups. Around 16% of apps have implemented the digital map UI pattern (Gaigg 2023) attribute filter and 66% use zoom controls. Despite being natively developed for Android, only 87% of apps use Google Maps. Other map platforms that can be integrated into Android applications and were used by the students are MapBox, osmdroid and Leaflet.

Figure 3. Temporal development of map task categories of all student projects.

2.4. Geographic Reference

Half of the student projects focus on a city (82% of them to Dresden) and just under a quarter have a global reference. Global apps tend to have the purpose of collecting data and are therefore not limited to a specific area, or they directly access APIs such as the OSM Overpass API, as any other data collection would be too extensive on a global scale.

Furthermore, the origin of the students can be compared with the geographic reference of their app. Figure 4 visualises this reduced to continents, whereby Dresden and Germany are listed separately for the geographic app reference, as many of the student projects relate to these because at the time of development the students are studying in that city/country. It can therefore be seen that most students place the topic of their mobile map application in their familiar surroundings, likely in order to simplify data collection and ensure relevance to their everyday lives.

Figure 4. Origin of the students in relation to the geographical reference of the created mobile map application.

3. Conclusions

Initial analysis of the student-created mobile map apps reveals both similarities and differences with global trends. The differences are largely due to the constraints imposed by being part of a university course. Students' digital native status and their professional ties make the apps a valuable source of insight. The high level of motivation and creativity in student work stands out: the students created solutions, filling gaps they identified, tailored to their interests while applying technical skills.

Some of these apps facilitate data collection, turning smartphones into versatile and user-centric devices: users actively contribute their own information rather than just passively consuming it. This trend of user-generated content was already described in 2009 and has been intensified with increasing smartphone use (Coleman & Georgiadou 2009; Melumad et al. 2019).

Even though mobile map apps are part of everyday life, their development is demanding: mobile UI design principles are pivotal and imply particular challenges. Thus, students' contributions reflect how mobile apps evolve technically and thematically.

UI designers, app developers, cartographers and educational institutions can gain insights from the study: what design and usage patterns young people prefer in mobile map apps, emerging cartographic developments, and how students learn through app development. Future work may include a comparison of teaching content with similar courses at other universities.

References

- Coleman D. & Georgiadou Y. (2009): Volunteered Geographic Information: The Nature and Motivation of Producers. *International Journal of Spatial Data Infrastructures Research*: 332–358.
- Gaigg M. (2023): *Designing Map Interfaces: Patterns for Building Effective Map Apps*. ESRI, Incorporated.
- Huang Z. & Benyoucef M. (2023): A systematic literature review of mobile application usability: Addressing the design perspective. *Universal Access in the Information Society* 22 (3): 715–735.
- Huseynov F. (2020): Understanding Usage Behavior of Different Mobile Application Categories Based on Personality Traits. *Interacting with Computers* 32 (1): 66–80.
- Melumad S., Inman J.J. & Pham M.T. (2019): Selectively Emotional: How Smartphone Use Changes User-Generated Content. *Journal of Marketing Research* 56 (2): 259–275.
- Perea P. & Giner P. (2017): *UX design for mobile: Design apps that deliver impressive mobile experiences*. Birmingham, UK: Packt Publishing.
- Statista (2023): *Number of mobile app downloads worldwide from 2019 to 2027, by segment*. <https://www.statista.com/forecasts/1262881/mobile-app-download-worldwide-by-segment> (visited on 19 February 2025).
- Statista (2024): *Most popular Google Play app categories as of 2nd quarter 2024, by share of available apps*. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/279286/google-play-android-app-categories/> (visited on 4 April 2025).
- Xu R., Frey R.M., Fleisch E. & Ilic A. (2016): Understanding the impact of personality traits on mobile app adoption – Insights from a large-scale field study. *Computers in Human Behavior* 62 (2): 244–256.